

EMERGING PRACTICES OF SCHOOL HEADS IN IMPROVING THE LITERACY SKILLS OF GRADES 1-3 LEARNERS IN THE DIGITAL AGE

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Emerging Practices of School Heads in Improving the Literacy Skills of Grades 1-3 Learners in the Digital Age

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Abstract

This study examined the numerous practices employed by the school heads in enhancing the literacy skills of Grades 1-3 learners in today's educational setting. It aimed to answer the questions about the existing problems of Grades 1-3 learners in literacy skills, methods and approaches used by teachers to address these problems and the emerging practices of school heads to improve the literacy skills of Grades 1-3 learners. Using quantitative research design, data were gathered among 40 school heads and 40 Grades 1-3 teachers of the 3rd congressional district of Masbate province. It utilized two surveys: the methods and approaches used by teachers to address these problems and the emerging practices of school heads to improve the literacy skills of Grades 1-3 learners and analyzed the results using the Five-Point Likert scale. This tool evaluated teachers' methods and approaches used in addressing the literacy problems and emerging practices and approaches used by the school heads to improve the literacy skills of the early-grade learners. The results revealed that reading comprehension and spelling are identified as the most significant challenges among learners, meanwhile, alphabet knowledge is the least encountered problem. To solve this, school heads implemented strategies which include leading effective practices in school and providing regular and constructive feedback wherein both were perceived as highly effective. The study concluded that instructional leadership and professional collaboration play a crucial role to address the challenges in literacy and recommended to foster these mentioned practices to assist early-grade learners to develop their literacy skills.

Keywords: *literacy skills, instructional leadership, reading comprehension*

Introduction

Literacy skills are a person's ability to read, write, speak, listen, and understand language effectively. These skills enable people to interpret critical information and communicate clearly and form a foundation for personal, academic, and professional growth. As time changed, technology also developed and progressed. This paved way for people to improve and enhance their literacy skills with the use of newly refined techniques and strategies that are beneficial to learners, teachers, and school heads.

Kathleen Tyner (1998). Digital technologies push beyond alphabetic literacy to explore the way that sound, image, and text can be incorporated into education. Attempts to redefine literacy terms--computer, information, technology, visual, and media literacies--proliferate and reflect the need to rethink entrenched assumptions about literacy. These multiple literacies are advanced to help users make sense of the information glut by fostering the ability to access, analyze, and produce communication in a variety of forms.

Sharp, Laurie A. (2014). 21st century learners arrive at school with technological knowledge and skills that necessitate the need for educational systems to transform instructional practices to meet learners' needs. The International Society for Technology in Education (ISTE) developed ISTE Standards for students, teachers, administrators, coaches, and computer science educators that define best practices and standards of excellence with technology. Literacy educators are greatly impacted by the technological shift in education and require a deep level of proficiency with the ISTE Standards for Teachers. The purpose of this article is to provide an overview of the ISTE Standards for Teachers and provide literacy educators with an evaluative tool to measure their adeptness with the knowledge and skills needed to teach in the digital age.

In the digital age in particular, school heads are essential in tackling literacy issues (Hew & Cheung, 2013). Technology integration (Kirschner & Wubbels, 2017), data-driven instruction (Hamilton et al., 2017), collaborative leadership (Hallinger & Murphy, 2013), and professional development (Guskey, 2014) are some of the emerging methods that school heads are implementing. These techniques are meant to improve reading abilities and get students ready for the digital world.

Proficient school administrators utilize digital resources to bolster literacy education, encourage online reading comprehension, and cultivate digital literacy abilities (Leu et al., 2017). Additionally, they support the development of literacy in communities and families (Henderson & Mapp, 2002). School administrators can enhance reading outcomes for students in Grades 1-3 by embracing innovation and teamwork.

Studies show that, especially in the digital era, school administrators must remain current on the best practices in literacy instruction (Kilpatrick, 2015). School administrators can foster a conducive learning environment, increase teacher effectiveness, and eventually raise student literacy by implementing cutting-edge procedures and technologies (Wiggins & McTighe, 2011).

Research Questions

This study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What are the existing problems of Grades 1-3 learners in literacy skills?
2. What are the methods and approaches used by teachers to address these problems?
3. What are the emerging practices of school heads to improve the literacy skills of Grades 1-3 learners?

Methodology

A quantitative method was applied in the study titled “Emerging Practices of School Heads in Improving the Literacy Skills of Grades 1-3 Learners in the Digital Age.” This research aimed to identify the existing problems of Grades 1-3 learners in literacy skills, determine the methods and approaches used by teachers to address these problems and ascertain the emerging practices of school heads to improve the literacy skills of Grades 1-3 learners.

The respondents were 40 grades 1-3 teachers and 40 school heads of the 3rd congressional district of Masbate Province covering the municipalities of Cataingan, Palanas, Uson, Dimasalang, Placer, Pio V. Corpuz, Esperanza and Cawayan. The respondents provided the needed information through the survey questionnaire which was disseminated using Google Forms. To ensure the validity and reliability of the survey, pilot testing was conducted before the proper data collection. In this research, the weighted mean, and Likert scale were employed in analyzing the data to determine any trend or pattern in response.

Participants were selected at random to ensure that the sample accurately reflects the population. Ethical considerations were followed throughout the study, with confidentiality and obtaining informed consent from all participants being fundamental to the process. The approach aimed to provide a clear and detailed understanding of how the school heads perceive and implement leadership in the current context.

Results and Discussion

This section presented the results and interpretation of the gathered data regarding the study. The data were presented and interpreted through tables, and weighted mean.

Table 1. Existing Problems of Grades 1-3 Learners in Literacy Skills

<i>Existing Problems of Grades 1-3 Learners in Literacy Skills</i>	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Oral Language	4.03	Agree
Phonemic Awareness	3.98	Agree
Alphabet Knowledge	3.71	Agree
Word Recognition	4.03	Agree
Vocabulary	4.15	Agree
Reading Fluency	4.03	Agree
Reading Comprehension	4.30	Strongly Agree
Listening Comprehension	4.08	Agree
Spelling	4.23	Strongly Agree
Writing	3.93	Agree

The findings of the study have shown that reading comprehension is strongly agreed upon by the respondents as an existing problem of Grades 1-3 learners in literacy skills, which got the highest weighted mean of 4.30. Other existing problems that got high agreements with the weighted mean of 4.23 are the spelling of the learners. On the findings shown above, the least existing problem that has been agreed upon by the respondents with the lowest weighted mean of 3.71 is the alphabet knowledge. It appeared from these findings that reading comprehension and spelling are the main existing problems in Grades 1-3 learners that teachers encountered.

According to Gough (Gough Tunmer, 1986; Hoover Gough, 1990), two-component skills—language comprehension and decoding—account for the vast majority of variability in children’s reading comprehension. According to the Simple View, difficulties in oral language predict poor reading comprehension, whereas difficulties in phonological skills and phonics predict poor decoding. Reading comprehension is a dynamic process and is a multidimensional construct. It is affected by the text adopted, the comprehension tasks used, and the processing demands of the assessment (Cain & Oakhill, 2006). Difficulty in this area may be due to a deficit in any number of underlying factor(s). Common to reading as well as spelling in all alphabetic orthographies is that both rely on understanding the alphabetic principle and learning the grapheme-phoneme correspondences (GPC) for spelling. According to developmental models (Ehri, 1995; Frith, 1985; Scheerer-Neumann006), acquiring these skills at the beginning of literacy instruction characterizes the alphabetic phase, which enables children to divide words into their constituent phonemes and assign the corresponding graphemes. Thus, training precursor skills, especially phoneme awareness and letter-sound knowledge together with systematic phonics instruction, builds the foundation for reading and spelling and significantly improves these skills in children with reading and spelling disorders across orthographies (Caravolas, 2004; Galuschka et al., 2014, 2020; Hatcher et al., 1994; Torgesen et al., 2001).

From these findings, the implication is that reading comprehension and spelling of the learners rely on the understanding of the alphabet

and learning. Thus, reading skills, especially phoneme awareness and letter-sound knowledge together with systematic phonics instruction, build the foundation for reading and spelling of a learner. However, this study has a limitation in that it reflects the perception of the respondents, who may not have fully represented the experiences of all those who may hold different views or be situated in different contexts. Also, limited to the third (3) congressional district of Masbate Province. Based on the results, reading comprehension and spelling problems are prevalent among students in Grades 1-3, hindering their academic progress. These difficulties often stem from inadequate instructional support. If left unaddressed, these challenges can lead to learning gaps, decrease motivation, and cause long-term academic struggles. Thus, it is recommended that educators and parents can work together to address reading comprehension and spelling challenges, fostering a strong foundation for future academic success.

Table 2. Methods and Approaches Used by Teachers to Address Literacy Problems

<i>Methods and Approaches Used by Teachers to Address Literacy Problems</i>	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Phonics	4.25	Strongly Agree
Reading Aloud	4.25	Strongly Agree
Explicit Teaching	4.35	Strongly Agree
Graphic Organizers	4.10	Agree
Language Experience Approach	4.28	Strongly Agree
Whole Language Approach	4.08	Agree
Decoding Strategies	4.15	Agree
Comprehension Strategies	4.28	Strongly Agree
Fluency Instruction	4.20	Agree
Technology-based Instruction	4.08	Agree

The data above showed that the methods and approaches used by teachers is 50% strongly agreed based on the data gathered from the respondents. However, 50% of them answered for agree. For the given data, you can see that phonics instruction, reading aloud, explicit teaching, language experience approach, and comprehension strategies are the most helpful methods and approaches used by the teachers. Other methods and approaches such as graphic organizers, whole language approach, decoding strategies, fluency instruction, and technology-based instruction rated also positively but lower for the standard of the teachers.

“What We Know and Need to Know about Literacy Interventions for Elementary Students with Reading Difficulties” by Jeanne Wanzek and Sharon Vaughn (2023); Reviews recent meta-analyses and systematic reviews on reading and writing interventions for elementary students facing reading challenges, including those with dyslexia. The author synthesizes findings to shed light on effective literacy interventions and identify areas requiring further research.

According to Hoque (2016) declared that techniques drawn from several methods/approaches are frequently used by students to learn modern languages in class. Depending on the unique needs of their students, teachers choose techniques from a range of approaches. A teacher should be able to identify the instructional techniques which will best support a given learning objective.

Many studies have been conducted using repeated reading which is one of the oldest and the most effective methods (Akyol & Ketenoglu Kayabasi, 2018). The findings reported by these studies concur with the finding of the current study.

Studies support the fact that students' fluent reading problems negatively affect their reading comprehension level (Akyol & Bastug, 2015; Yildirim & Rasinski, 2017). Addressing the student's needs in learning to read in today's increasingly prominent classroom environment can be intricate and challenging learning obstacles. Children's ability to thrive from reading instruction can be affected by a number of obstacles, including emotional, behavioral, and intellectual disabilities (Brown, 2016).

From these findings, the implication is that graphic organizer, whole language approach, decoding strategies, fluency instruction and technology – based instruction were used by Grades 1-3 teachers to address literacy problems depends on the ability and performance of the learners to make them read. Thus, methods and approaches used by the Grades 1-3 teachers especially explicit teaching, comprehension strategies, language experience approaches, effective methods and approaches used by the teachers inside the classroom to help the learners how to read and understand what they are reading.

However, this study has a limitation because the results of our studies depends upon the responses of Grades 1-3 teachers in the 3rd Congressional District in Masbate Province. Based on the results, explicit teaching got the highest points among other methods and approaches used by the teachers in Grades 1-3 that is most effective in solving the literacy problems encountered by all teachers inside the classroom. That's why, it is recommended that teachers need to use methods and approaches suited to learning needs of the learners so that they can easily acquire literacy skills and also communicate to the parents/ guardians of the learners so that they have follow-up in their homes in assisting their child's progress in reading and comprehension.

The table 3 showed the emerging practices of school heads in improving the literacy skills of Grade 1 – 3 learners. Among the mentioned practices, indicator 4 (Lead Effective Practice in School) with 3.88 weighted mean, and indicator 8 (Provide Regular and Constructive Feedback) with 3.88 weight mean both received an interpretation of “agree” showing that these strategies are perceived as effective by the targeted respondents. Working closely with instructors results in improved instruction, superior teaching strategies, and meaningful learning according to both measures.

Table 3. *Emerging Practices of School Heads to Improve the Literacy Skills of Grades 1-3 Learners*

<i>Emerging practices of school heads to improve the literacy skills of Grades 1-3 learners</i>	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Work directly with teachers to strengthen their teaching practice	3.8	Agree
Implement high-quality instructional approaches	3.65	Agree
Offer meaningful professional development opportunities	3.78	Agree
Lead effective practices in school	3.88	Agree
Set a culture of collaboration and high expectations.	3.73	Agree
Encourage creation of cozy reading corners	3.78	Agree
Provide frequent distributed practice of skills	3.75	Agree
Provide regular and constructive feedback	3.88	Agree
Regularly monitor reading progress	3.75	Agree
Analyze student data with the aim of improving instruction.	3.73	Agree

Effective leadership techniques, such as enhancing working circumstances and offering mentorship, resulted in successful and efficient teaching jobs, according to Severino (2023). Meantime, school heads who provide feedback to teachers' performance is perceived as useful by teachers themselves that could contribute to their professional development and school improvement (Tuytens & Devos, 2017). This also emphasized the important role of school heads in ensuring effective teaching methods and achieving smooth teaching and learning process.

Moreover, other practices also received "agree" among the respondents highlighted the effectiveness of these strategies in the improvement of Grade 1 -3 literacy skills. Overall, all strategies suggested a holistic approach encompassing the key factors namely leadership, teacher support, and student engagement – these are all vital in addressing literacy challenges and resulting to improved literacy and reading skills. As Prabowo et. al. (2023) mentioned, school administrators encourage instructors and students to participate completely in all literacy-development activities by fostering a positive learning environment.

Gading (2024) asserts that in order to implement successful instructional leadership, school administrators must engage closely with teachers, to promote a culture of cooperation and shared accountability for student success. Teachers are in need of school leaders who can guide and help them perform their work effectively to make improvements on the part of their students' learning. As stated by Dellomas & Deri (2022), school heads are expected to dispense wide array of competencies in the performance of duties in order to realize the long-coveted aim for quality and life-long learners. According to Parveen et. al. (2024), school administrators and teachers should utilize quality practices in their work with students. It is the school head and teachers' collaboration that will motivate them to help students achieve academically.

Meantime, as stated by Gading (2024), giving feedback on the performance of teachers entirely gave the teachers ideas on how to enhance their performance which in return improved the performance of the learners. Gonfa (2020) asserts that feedback is an essential component in all learning contexts and without feedback of any kind, we would end up doomed to repeat the same mistakes over and over again. Providing feedback helps teachers improve their teaching competence to effect maximum learning.

From these findings, the implication is that school leaders who lead effective practices in school and provide regular and constructive feedback help improve learners' performance in literacy skills. However, this study has a limitation in that it reflects the perceptions of the respondents who may not have fully represented the experiences of all those who may hold different views or are situated in different contexts. Also, this is limited to the third (3rd) congressional district of Masbate Province. Based on the results, the emerging practices of school heads to improve the literacy skills of Grades 1-3 learners are leading effective practices in school and providing regular and constructive feedback. These practices of school heads foster a culture of continuous improvement and enhance instructional quality and support student progress in literacy development.

Conclusions

Based on the statistical results of the study, the following conclusions were drawn:

Difficulty in reading comprehension and spelling are considered as the major barriers to the literacy development in early grades.

The need to strengthen the foundational literacy skills through the identified teaching methods and approaches in order to address the challenges.

School heads had an important role in improving the literacy abilities of the learners by means of effective practices and providing meaningful and constructive feedback among the teachers.

In light of the foregoing findings and conclusions, the following are recommended:

Teachers have to utilize varied and appropriate instructional materials to help the learners develop their literacy skills.

Teachers need to implement a systematized phonics-based strategies and approaches focusing on phonics awareness, sounds, and spelling to develop strong literacy foundations.

School heads may strengthen their instructional leadership by fostering collaboration among teachers and ensuring that regular and constructive feedback to achieve quality teaching.

Future Studies may expand the scope of the research by including a broader demographic factors such as gender and parents' profiles to provide comprehensive understanding of the literacy challenges and effective interventions.

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